

Individualism, Family Ties and Social Tension: A Comparative Study between the USA and Turkey

Abstract

Individualism has increased culturally in different societies due to modern advancements in technology, lifestyle, and values. Sociologically, there is always worry about how this affects people's personal and collective well-being, such as family relationships, depression, and suicidal tendencies. This study also attempts to investigate the same issue using a distinct approach. This article used Hofstede's individualism/collectivism dimensions and scores to examine the divorce and single-parent rates worldwide and explore the pattern of family relations between the two sides. Similarly, we also explored the global depression and suicide rates using Hofstede's IDV index. Finally, we compared two culturally opposing countries, the United States and Turkey, using IDV scores and rankings in the different surveys and provided theoretical justification and insight into the results. According to the findings of this study, individualist countries are most likely to have fewer family bonds and suffer from higher socio-psychological tensions such as depression and suicide.

Keywords: Individualism, family ties, social tension, comparative culture, United States, Turkey, collectivism, family structure, cultural values, social transformation

Introduction

The family, the most primitive institution of human civilization, was historically responsible for providing food, shelter, and reasonable education and clothing for a helpless human baby. In the last century, surprisingly, the nature of family has significantly changed in certain areas of the world, particularly in Western Society. Yet, Kitayama and Markus (1995) argue that many cultures worldwide still consider social context and interconnection more important than individual needs. Others, specifically societies influenced by Western values, embraced individuality rather than family and a collectivist way of life. In short, globalization has expanded through different forms of political, economic, and technological advancement worldwide, and that has had a huge influence on blurring work-family obligations and responsibilities (Ollier-Malaterre et al., 2013).

Hofstede et al. (2010) define *individualism* as a cultural orientation in which individuals prioritize their objectives over those of the group, cultivating a sense of personal autonomy and independence. Individualism is also defined "as a preference for independence, pursuing one's own personal goals above the needs of a community, and maintaining relationships with others only when the costs do not outweigh the benefits" (Triandis & Gelfand, 1998, p. 118). In contrast, *collectivism* is defined as an orientation towards groups and goals shared by a group. Collectivism underscores the importance of group cohesion and interdependence, with family and social bonds playing a critical role in the organization of daily life (Hofstede et al., 2010). In the families of individualist societies, kids depend on the family as far as they can manage their own cost of living. After that, they maintain a distant relationship with their parents and sometimes fully break them off (Hofstede et al., 2010). Undoubtedly, this indicates the loosening of family ties in an individualistic society.

In psychological research, modernist theorists argue that rising individualism is a consequence of modern and economic development around the world, where people are becoming more individualistic rather than societal or family-oriented (Hamamura, 2012). Hofstede et al.'s (2010) work on the cultural dimension also explored individualism and collectivism in different parts of the world and how those characteristics are deeply rooted in

culture. That is called *the Individualism versus Collectivism (IDV)* dimension, which is one of the major dimensions of Hofstede's famous six cultural dimensions regarding different cultures and how that works as software of the mind in various contexts of life (i.e., leadership, management, family dynamics, and organization). While studying Hofstede's cultural dimensions, certain countries, especially those that are economically and institutionally most developed, such as Norway and the United States, have one thing in common. That is the journey towards more freedom, equality, rapid independence from family dependency and value, and so on, which vastly resembles their individualistic way of social pattern. These features greatly influence family structure in most parts of the world. From a socio-psychological view, family ties have a particular impact on human life, both social and personal. Although some cultures have different orientations towards this, somehow loosening family ties has a social impact. For instance, according to Hofstede et al. (2010), individualistic societies use more Internet, and that pushes toward less family communication, weaker social circles, more indications of depression, and vulnerable feelings of loneliness (Kraut et al., 1998). Similarly, in individual societies, people usually relocate frequently because of social culture, career development, technological advancement, and so on. This circle disrupts social networks, raises stress and family tensions, and increases the likelihood of developing depression, at least in women (Weissman, 1972).

However, Hidaka (2012a) mentions that while freedom is admirable, it appears to be a double-edged sword, as an excessive choice can lead to paralytic indecision, increased expectations, stress, depression, and eventual dissatisfaction, blame, and regret (Schwartz, 2000). Those characteristics can easily lead to increased rates of depression, anxiety, social dysfunction, decreased well-being, and suicide (Zeelenberg et al., 2000) (Kasser, 2003). Given the context, this research exclusively uses Hofstede's (2010) cultural dimension score to shed light on family ties and explores how individualism can lead to weak family ties to socio-psychological issues like depression and suicide with a comparative analysis between the United States and Turkey.

Literatures Review

Individualism is the belief that individuals are separate beings with personal differences that make him/her unique from the group. Internal processes guide individualists' behaviors, with the goal of reaching self-satisfaction and one's full potential. *Collectivism* is defined as a social pattern consisting of closely interconnected individuals in a group. Collectivists gain their values and social norms from the group (Cheng et al., 2020, p. 287). Since Hofstede's (1980) ground-breaking work, the concept of *individualism* versus *collectivism* has been a central focus in cross-cultural psychology. This dimension explains how cultural differences affect individuals' psychological outcomes, social relationships, and ideas of self worldwide. Individualism prioritizes personal autonomy, independence, and self-reliance, whereas collectivism prioritizes interdependence, group cohesion, and the priority of family or societal requirements over individual desires (Hofstede et al., 2010).

While discussing individualism-collectivism, societal differences in this study psychologically discussed as *Self-Culture* (Ratanasiripong, 1997), and *dependent-interdependent* (Markus & Kitayama, 1991) to determine the effect of cultural and social variation on the psychology of people all over the world. To go deeper into this distinction, Triandis (1995) divided the self into three parts: *private self*, *public self*, and *communal self*. However, the differentiation between cultures and the impact of culture on personal mood and behavior is not a new occurrence in the area of psychology. Recently, psychologists have begun to focus on cross-cultural differences and human behavior and events that have significant psychological consequences (i.e., Brislin & Yoshida, 1994; Hofstede, 1980; Miyake & Yamazaki, 1995; Shweder, 1990; Shaver et al., 1992; Shaver et al., 1992). Despite the fact that much research has been conducted on cross-cultural challenges, Hofstede's psychological discoveries and mapping of distinct dimensions have had a significant impact on relevant scholarly debate.

However, since Hofstede's cultural dimension was published in 1980, it has been utilized worldwide to examine various cultures, contexts, dimensions, and disciplines. There have been numerous studies that link Hofstede's cultural factor with family ties and developing socio-psychological issues worldwide (depression and suicide rates). While reviewing the literature for the study, we have identified three basic themes from which, commonly, the idea of individualism and its relationship with family bonding and socio-psychological issues are explored and researched, such as individualism vs. family cohesion, freedom and social isolation, and family and social support. Literature reviews of the study also followed these

themes to move further in this research and make a more structured discussion. Some researchers used Hofstede's cultural dimension, and some did not.

Individualism and family cohesion

Individualism is an essential part of the Western world, and the journey toward more self-dependence is still growing in other parts of the world. Yet, people still face difficulties coping with the output of being free and having a personal goal-oriented lifestyle.

Researchers have extensively explored these outcomes of individualism. Farivar et al. (2016) explored the relationship between cultural characteristics and the underlying reasons for work-family balance issues in a rising non-western cultural context. They discovered a lack of social connection as a source of work-family imbalance. Similarly, Gu et al. (2022) investigate work-family conflict and happiness, as well as the moderating influence of national culture. Based on Hofstede's distinct dimensions, they discover that subjective well-being related to family life is lower in individualistic societies than in communal ones. Neftçi and Barnow (2016) examined the overall depression of Turkish immigrants in Europe and how it has ethnocultural characteristics that follow Hofstede's dimensions. A study using WVS data found that individualism is associated with looser family ties. It reduces family ties at individual and country levels (Davis & Williamson, 2020, p. 15). When families get broken, kids in those families face a great challenge in their different stages of life. Studies suggest that children from broken families face more depression in the future, and their common growing routine gets disturbed as well (Hymowitz, 2019). However, some studies find the opposite. For instance, Veenhoven (1999) and Schyns (1998) find that individualism has a positive relationship with well-being and happiness at both personal and family levels while controlling income in their analysis.

Freedom and social isolation

A large number of studies suggest that individualist characteristics such as more freedom and more importance to personal pursuit than family and collective responsibility have a significant role in an increasing number of social isolation, stress, anxiety, depression, and suicide in the West. To start with, Putnam (2000) is relevant, who argues against Inglehart that individualism eradicates the influence of people to join different types of communal engagement and devaluates the social spirit. Twenge (2011) argues and finds the result of the devaluation of spirits. He states, 'something about modern Western life is causing more and more young people to feel anxious and depressed' (p. 469). Following that argument, Bellah

(1992) demonstrates in his book 'Good Society' how individualism and modern thinking of Americans on families deviate from society. He includes homelessness, unemployment, frustration, empathy for others, and so on (Claire & Velasquez, 2022). A study by Beck & Beck-Gernsheim (2002) demonstrates that there is a strong link between individualism and loneliness, poor social support, and high probabilities of family conflict and divorce. Following the same trend, multiple studies (i.e., Debra & Thomeer (2020); Eckersley R & K. (2002); Lykes & Kemmelmeier (2014); Scott et al. (2004)) suggest that individualism and the individualist nature of social trends in different societies lead individuals to be more prone to stress, isolation, depression, and suicidal tendency and suicide. However, multiple research also shows the other side of the story and social context; for example, Veenhoven, R. (1999) illustrates that the quality of life is way better in an individualistic society. Moreover, the individualistic nature of a social system is the key to individual happiness and well-being. The more independent the nation, the more freedom and happiness its citizens enjoy. That also helps to work individuals for more national glory and advancement in most sectors compared to other nations. This study was done in the context of the USA (Mennell, 2020). Even though this study is not directly relevant to this theme yet, while we are discussing social isolation, this study shows that maybe someone can detach from his/her family, but he or she can work more for the nation where the nation is just basically a bigger institution of family. But the question remains: How does that affect an individual's psychological well-being? This study will try to find the answer to a descriptive manner.

Family, collectivism, and social support

While discussing individualism and collectivism, researchers discovered that collectivism acts as a substantial preventive strategy against depression. Knyazev et al. (2017) show that the country's collectivist characteristics play a significant role in cases of depression. Frank and Hou (2019) discovered that the level of depression is higher when a person is from an individualistic country, and migrants from collective countries tend to have higher depression initially because of primary cultural shock (individualistic). They also used Hofstede's assessment to identify collective and individual countries. Talking about family, specifically family bonding, helps individuals to come out of problematic tendencies and defend themselves against negative aspects resulting from postmodernity, such as social isolation, anxiety, depression, and so on (Sorys, 2020). Debra Thomeer (2020) also shows that strong family ties act as a protective measure for an individual's mental well-being. Similarly, suicide attempts probability is also decreased by family attachment. The protective effect of

family ties and support on suicidal conduct is dramatically mitigated by collective and interactive efficacy (Maimon D et al., 2010). In the instance of the association between divorce and suicide, research suggests that divorced people are more likely to commit suicide, and culture also plays a role in this, where Hofstede's cultural dimension is also being used (Yip et al., 2015). Pirani (2015) conducted a psychological study that demonstrates the social bonds and family support of disabled people in socioeconomic and regional variances in Italy using the same dimension measure. Conversely, some scholars have also brought a number of nuanced findings regarding family, collectivism, and personal well-being from different parts of the world. According to Ahuvia, A. (2002), collectivism is generally more prevalent in Third World and developing countries, where family ties are strong, but still, research suggests that these societies are also prone to socio-psychological issues such as depression, divorce, and suicide due to economic instability. Thus, it is evident that income and economic well-being also play a significant role in the psychological well-being of people in a particular culture and society. Study with young people from Western countries shows that male youth suicide has a negative correlation with individualism (Eckersley R & K., 2002).

Hence, exploring the relationship between individualism, family ties, and socio-psychological problems is a multi-dimensional discourse in psychological study. However, as there has been a lack of enough studies on describing the pattern of relationship between individualism and family ties and socio-psychological issues (i.e., depression and suicide) based on Hofstede's individualism index, this study attempts to address the research gap by comparing two countries that are in the opposite row on the IDV index along with theoretical explanation based on existing literature. Therefore, the study chose the United States and Turkey because these two countries are essentially on the opposite side of the chosen dimensions. Furthermore, the United States and Turkey have significant cultural variations that influence findings based on their cultural perspectives, even though they share several modern principles such as democracy, secularism, and institutional structure and characteristics (specifically or constitutionally).

Theoretical Discussion

Culture

Culture is a vastly contested idea that varies into different schools of thought. Thus, providing a unified or standard definition of culture is difficult. Although it includes certain generally used meanings such as "*civilization*" or "*mind refinement*" (Hofstede et al., 2010, p.5). Since culture is employed from a socio-psychological perspective in this study, the definition of culture must be drawn or adopted from the same perspective. Some define *culture* as a whole way of human life. According to Smith and Riley (2009), culture is basically "the entire way of life, activities, beliefs, and customs of a people, group, or society" cf. (Yip et al., 2015, p.88). Others argue that culture is the pattern of mental processes, customs, and traditions of specific groups of people. The definition by Kroeber and Kluckhohn (1952) provides a core theme of culture from hundreds of definitions, which is "Culture consists of explicit and implicit patterns of historically derived and selected ideas and their embodiment in institutions, practices, and artifacts" (Adams & Markus, 2004, p. 341).

According to Hofstede et al. (2010), culture is a communal phenomenon since it is shared among those who live or have lived in the same social area where it was taught. It is composed of unwritten social game rules. More specifically, culture is the "collective programming of the mind that distinguishes members of one group or category of people from others" (Hofstede et al., 2010, pp. 5-6). Following that, it is clear that culture is a distinct manifestation and way of life of people from a specific region. That is, culture differs one group of people from another in terms of lifestyle, customs, and thought patterns. According to Goldberger and Veroff (1995), culture is always produced in part by the realization of outsiders that the group is "different" and independent from outside observers on one or more dimensions (p.10-11).

Hofstede's Cultural Dimension

Culture, according to Hofstede, is mental software. He also analyzes the geographical, ethnic, and religious differences contributing to a society's cultural impression and expression. More specifically, Hofstede (1980) and Hofstede et al. (2010) conducted one of the most comprehensive assessments of how culture influences societal values, from individual lifestyle to various social, public, and private practices and organizations. He gives a significant deal of rational and empirical evidence to determine four (1980) and then six (2010) separate dimensions for assessing national culture from diverse regions of the world. The six dimensions are as follows: power distance, uncertainty avoidance,

individualism/collectivism, masculinity/femininity, long/short-term orientation, and indulgence/restraint. These six cultural aspects suggest differential preferences for one condition of affairs over another, distinguishing countries from one another. Individualism versus collectivism is used extensively in this study to examine the effect on the socio-psychological behavior of citizens of indexed countries. Recent studies have expanded Hofstede's framework to investigate the effect of this cultural dimension on people's social behavior and mental health. Collectivist societies provide strong support systems that may act as protective measures against different mental and psychological issues, even though these societies have some form of limitations in personal freedom compared to individualist ones (Knyazev et al., 2017). In contrast, according to Minkov & Hofstede (2011), while individual societies have space for more personal freedom, they may also promote feelings of isolation, loneliness, and stress. That can potentially be resulting high rates of depression and suicide.

Individualism versus Collectivism

Individualism and collectivism can be defined as a specific and cultural approach to describing a group of people's social and psychological processes (Triandis, 1995). Individualism, more precisely, can be defined as a preference for a loosely knit social system in which people are primarily expected to care for themselves and their immediate families. Children in this society grow up with the sense of "I" and are not dependent on any organization. Collectivism, on the other hand, favors a close-knit social structure in which individuals can expect their family or members of a specific group to care for them in exchange for unquestioning allegiance. Children typically grow up with a sense of "we" (Hofstede et al., 2010, p. 91). Geert Hofstede used IBM data to make his index on different countries. Collective poles have the most influence on personal time, freedom, and challenge, according to that dataset. Conversely, the collective side of the countries places a high value on training, physical fitness, and skill use (Hofstede et al., 2010, p. 93). This shows an opposing pattern of psychiatric conditions and cultural expression.

Research Method and Design

The study uses a quantitative research design that employs quantitative descriptive analysis and examines the relationship pattern between individualism and family ties. It also investigates the socio-psychological issues that arise from this cultural and sociological shift,

such as depression and suicide. For this type of research, descriptive analysis with theoretical interpretation is useful since it enables the quantification of observed patterns (such as divorce rates, single-parent families, depression, and suicide), a more thorough examination of the socio-cultural and theoretical contexts in which these trends take place (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011);(Creswell & Creswell, 2018), as well as in a comparative context between two different cases (USA and Turkiye). In current research, this design is complementarity, whereby the interpretative theoretical and socio-cultural theme explains the patterns seen in the quantitative data theories like Hofstede's cultural dimensions and studies on individualism and collectivism. In short, the study employs quantitative data to uncover social patterns and connect to theoretical themes established in the existing literature. However, as this research only tried to find a relationship pattern and provided a theoretical explanation of it, it does not have any hypothesis testing and causal inference. In this study, individualism is measured through IDV scores. Following the literature review and research objective, family ties are measured by Divorce and Single Parents rates of the country and psychological issues are measured through depression and suicide rates.

Data Collection and Analysis

The current analysis uses four secondary data sources. Combining these multiple data sets allows for a systematic cross-national investigation of individualism's effect on family relationships and psychological outcomes. The United States and Turkey were chosen as case countries because of their opposite positions in the IDV scores. One of the key research objectives is to see the impact on families in different cultural and familial contexts based on their great diversity in social and cultural spheres. Nevertheless, nations with high IDV scores are selected for cross-national studies, where the top 29 individualist countries have been taken into consideration to see the relationship with the variables of the study. In case of Divorce rates over 50 and below 50 form the selection criteria, and for depression and suicide, measurement was over 90 and below 90. The authors taken these measurements based on the number of countries included in the datasets. Data sets are searched and selected depending on convenience, relevance, consistency, and up-to-date information, ensuring the research's accuracy and reliability. The study data sets cover more than eighty percent of the global population, which helps to ensure a level of validity of the study results.

Hofstede's Cultural Insights (2010):

The basis for understanding and employing cultural orientation in a global context is the Individualism versus Collectivism (IDV) index, developed by Greet Hofstede. Based on the degree to which societies value individual pursuits over group bonding, countries are ranked according to their IDV ratings (Hofstede & Minkov, 2010). Among the Six dimensions of Hofstede's Insight, the first four (i.e., power distance, uncertainty avoidance, individualism/collectivism, masculinity/femininity) are based on IBM research and replications from 76 countries and regions; the last two (i.e., long/short-term orientation, and indulgence/restraint) are based on World Value Survey, and scores are given for 93 cases. According to the IDV index, Turkiye is on the side of the collectivist (IDV: 37), whereas the USA is on the list of the individualistic (IDV: 91) countries. The relationship between cultural individualism and socio-psychological consequences is primarily based on Hofstede's IDV score.

World Population Review (2022). - Divorce Rates:

Divorce rates identified per 1000 individuals from respective countries were used as an indicator of weakening family ties. World Population Review has a huge secondary dataset in different categories. They usually update their data every year. According to their website, they used data from Demographic Yearbook 2022, United Nations Demographic Yearbook 2020, Pew Research Divorce Demography, OECD Marriage and Divorce, and the National Center for Health Statistics (US CDC) (Divorce Rates by Country 2024). As a unit of analysis, divorce rates are compared across countries with high and low IDV scores. The relationship between individualism and weakening family ties was explored using divorce rates.

Pew Research Center Report (2019) - Single-Parent Households:

In this study, another important measure of weakening family ties is the proportion of children raised by single parents. This report and its statistics come from the analysis source of the Pew Research Centre. It includes multiple indicator cluster surveys, demographic and health surveys, census data archived by IPUMS International, general social surveys, European social surveys, and country-specific studies. Pew's study covered 91% of the global population. The single-parent rate in this research was correlated with countries based on their position on the IDV list by Hofstede Insight.

World Population Review (2022). - Depression and Suicide Rates:

Depression and suicide rates are two measures of the study, which resemble the socio-psychological issues in any society. To explore the relationship with IDV scores, depression rate per total population and Suicide rate per 100000 people are also employed by World Population Review. In the case of depression, they used data from Depression and Other Common Mental Disorders - Global Health Estimates and for suicide rate World Health Organization (Suicide Rates 2019), World Health Statistics (World Health Organization).

Data Analysis

The study's data analysis consists of two steps: quantitative descriptive analysis and theoretical interpretation of the identified pattern from descriptive analysis. The main focus of this approach is identifying trends or patterns and interpreting those data in the context of relevant cultural and psychological theories.

Quantitative Descriptive Analysis

In this section, the study presents the quantitative descriptive table and report where Individualist countries are presented and explored based on the divorce rate, single-parent households, depression rate, and suicide rate. That helps us to understand the underlying relationship between family bonding and mental health issues within individualist and collective societies.

Individualism and Divorce rate

This article assesses data on the global divorce rate and single-parent children to understand the relationship pattern between them. The authors synthesized the table according to analytical framework and data sets are used from the World Population Survey and the Pew Research Report.

Top Individualist Countries			Divorce Rate
Index Serial	Country	Position in the survey	Num. of Divorce Per 1000 population (Low) 0.15-----5.52 (High)
1.	United States	13	2.7
2.	Australia	37	1.9
3.	United	52	1.7

	Kingdom		
4.	Canada	27	2.1
5.	Netherlands	50	1.7
6.	New Zealand	46	1.7
7.	Italy	68	1.4
8.	Belgium	5	3.7
9.	Denmark	12	2.7
10.	France	39	1.9
11.	Sweden	18	2.5
12.	Ireland	97	0.7
13.	Latvia	10	2.7
14.	Norway	36	1.9
15.	Switzerland	31	2
16.	Germany	53	1.7
17.	South Africa	102	0.6
18.	Finland	19	2.4
19.	Estonia	35	1.9
20.	Lithuania	11	2.7
21.	Luxembourg	20	2.3
22.	Poland	51	1.7
23.	Malta	94	0.7
24.	Czech Republic	33	2
25.	Austria	49	1.7

26.	Hungary	62	1.5
27.	Israel	41	1.8
28.	Slovakia	47	1.7
29.	Spain	38	1.9

Table 1. Researcher's Synthesis on Individualist countries versus Divorce rate (World population review 2022¹ and hofstedes IDV index²)

To demonstrate the relationship pattern between individualist nations and divorce rates, first and foremost, the study uses Hofstede's (2010) IDV index to rank countries to determine whether they are more or less individual. This research chose the top 29 nations based on their individualism score and rank; more specifically, we picked countries from the Individualism index whose score is fifty or above. This research chose one region of Belgium and followed a random rank from the index based on their serial and score to make it easy, whereas Hofstede differed somewhat. As a result, Spain's position in the IDV index is 32, whereas it is 29th in our rating. Second, the study used a world population review study on worldwide divorce to calculate the divorce rates of the top 29 nations, whereas they obtained divorce percentages for 107 countries. To measure the divorce rate among 29 nations, this study employs the Top Fifty measurement, which indicates that if one of the selected countries ranks higher than fifty in the divorce survey, it is on the lower end of the scale. In the same way, if it is within fifty, it suggests they are on the high side of the rate.

To summarize the data in the table, there is not a particularly significant pattern of relationship between divorce rate and individualism score, although there is a visible pattern of relationship in our observation. Most studies selected nations are in the top fifty in terms of divorce rate per 1000 inhabitants. Only six nations are ranked outside of the Top Fifty, with South Africa (102) and Ireland (97) surprisingly ranking on the opposite side of the divorce rate of most individual countries. In contrast, Latvia(10), Lithuania(11), the United States(13), and Finland(19) are all in the top twenty. The rest have a more or less moderate divorce rate, while the majority are among the top fifty. As a result, top individualistic nations are experiencing more divorce than

¹<https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/divorce-rates-by-country>

² Individualism Index (IDV) Values, Table 4.1, Hofstede, 2010, p. 96,

top collectivist ones. So, this research discovered a pattern in the relationship between divorce and individuality, although it is not a casual relationship.

Individualism and Single parents

To measure the relationship between individuality and single parents, this study is unable to uncover any survey data to support, such as divorce or suicide rates. Nonetheless, we discovered a detailed report regarding single-parent children that is very significant here. The Pew Research Center recently published research that investigated children living in single-parent families in over 130 nations (Karmer, 2019). They displayed it on a worldwide map. We also provided that in the article (Map 1). The global view of single-parent children reveals that the US (23%) has the highest rate of children living in single-parent families, whereas it is also the most individualistic country in the world. Similarly, the UK (21%), Denmark (17), France (16%), Ireland (14%), and Germany (12%) also have high percentages of children living with single parents who are also in the top position in the individualism index. 4th most individualistic country, Canada, also shares 15% of children living in single-parent families. Only Sao Tome & Principe (19%), Russia (18%), and Kenya (16%) have a relatively similar rate to the less individualist countries. Whereas the global average is 6.8%. On the contrary, Mali, Afghanistan (1%), and Turkey (2%) have the lowest percentages of children who are living with single parents. Thus, according to the Pew Research Center's study which covers 95% population of the world, there is a significant pattern of relationship between individualism and single-parent households. More individualistic countries tend to have more children living with a single parent than

Almost a quarter of U.S. children live in single-parent homes, more than in any other country

% of children under age 18 in single-parent households

Note: Single-parent households include one adult and at least one biological, step or foster child under 18. Adult children may be present, but no other relatives or non-relatives.

Source: Pew Research Center analysis of 2010-2018 census and survey data. See methodology for details.

"Religion and Living Arrangements Around the World"

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- *Map 1: Children living in Single Parent households³*

collectivist countries. However, after providing a brief descriptive view, to see the visible relationship between family ties and individualism, this article chose two indicators, the divorce rate, which has a visible relationship with individualism, and single parents, which tend to have more strong relationship pattern with the percentage of individualism in different countries. From that perspective, this study finds that individualism is most likely related to family ties, and most individualistic countries tend to have weaker family ties.

Individualism and Socio-psychological Problems (Depression and Suicide)

Following the first section, this study again presents a table that employs a similar pattern of the top 29 countries selected from the IDV index and two distinct world population review survey data on global depression and suicide rates. Similarly, depending on their position in the survey, this research attempts to discover the relationship between top individualist countries and socio-psychological issues such as depression and suicide rates. In addition, in

³ Pew Research Center, <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2019/12/12/religion-and-living-arrangements-around-the-world/>

contrast to Table 1, the study used the Top Ninety measurement to measure our country's position on the depression and suicide ratio because more nations (179) were added to these two surveys.

Top Individualist Countries		Depression Rate		Suicide Rate	
Ind. Ser.	Country	Position in the survey	Percentage of cases in total population(%) <i>(Low) 2.90-6.30 (High)</i>	Position in the survey	Rate of Suicide per 100,000 people <i>(Low) 0.4-72.4(High)</i>
1.	United States	4	5.9	24	16.1
2.	Australia	3	5.9	40	12.5
3.	United Kingdom	86	4.5	86	7.9
4.	Canada	72	4.7	47	11.8
5.	Netherlands	71	4.7	46	11.8
6.	New Zealand	15	5.4	52	11
7.	Italy	35	5.1	100	6.7
8.	Belgium	61	4.8	17	18.3
9.	Denmark	42	5	56	10.7
10.	France	63	4.8	36	13.8
11.	Sweden	51	4.9	30	14.7
12.	Ireland	60	4.8	61	9.6
13.	Latvia	50	4.9	15	20.1
14.	Norway	68	4.7	45	11.8
15.	Switzerland	44	5	32	14.5
16.	Germany	22	5.2	42	12.3
17.	South Africa	80	4.6	10	23.5
18.	Finland	9	5.6	25	15.3
19.	Estonia	2	5.9	27	14.9
20.	Lithuania	8	5.6	7	26.1
21.	Luxembourg	37	5	50	11.3
22.	Poland	35	5.1	51	11.3
23.	Malta	24	5.1	107	6.1
24.	Czech Republic	20	5.2	NA	NA
25.	Austria	31	5.1	31	14.6
26.	Hungary	32	5.1	21	16.6

27.	Israel	77	4.6	125	5.3
28.	Slovakia	31	5.1	43	12.1
29.	Spain	21	5.20	88	7.7

- *Table 2. Researcher’s Synthesis on Individualist countries versus Depression and Suicide rate (World population review 2022 ,⁴⁵ and hofstedes IDV index⁶)*

To illustrate the table, in the first look, there is no significant pattern of relationship between individualism and depression and suicide rates. However, as previously noted, one can dive deep into it in a different way. For the depression rate, it’s clear that individualistic countries rank within the Top Ninety, whereas this survey collected data from 179 countries and displayed percentages compared to the entire population. That means the selected 29 countries are also on the highest side of the depression rate not on the lowest side. Similarly, for suicide, there are only three exceptions, such as Israel (125), Malta (107), and Italy (100), which exceeds the Top Ninety positions from 179 countries again. That pattern also indicates that, somehow, individualistic countries tend to have the highest rates of suicide in the world. In both cases, Lithuania (8 &7), Estonia (2&27), the United States (4&24), and Finland (9&25) score high in the world rankings of depression and suicide, according to the global population review. Surprisingly, the UK (86&86) and Austria (31&31) had the same position in both surveys. Similarly, most individualistic countries have relatively similar levels of depression and suicide rates, with the exception of Malta (24&107), South Africa (80&10), Israel (77&125), Spain (21&88), and Italy (35&100), though some of the countries have a visible distance between two surveys positions that are not significant in terms of scores. That suggests an underlying relationship pattern between individualism, depression, and suicide rates. Individualistic countries are likely to have a higher rate of depression and suicide than others.

Comparative Analysis between United States and Turkey

Scores of Hofstedes Index

⁴<https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/dipression-rates-by-country>

⁵ <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/suicide-rate-by-country>

⁶ Individualism Index (IDV) Values, Table 4.1, Hofstede, 2010, p. 96,

- *Image 1: Graphical presentation of US and Turkey's score in Hofstede's Insight*

According to the graphical presentation, it is evident that without the last dimension of indulgence and Restraint, the US and Turkey are relatively on the reverse side. Yet the study only dives further into the chosen dimension, "Individualism." Their difference is the highest among the six dimensions For individuals. That means Turkey (37) is mostly on the collectivist side, though it's not extremely collectivist, and the US (91) obviously is the top individualist country in the world. More specifically, for the US (91), this score has a lot of implications and influence in most parts of society. Based on this study, this score reveals that society is very weakly connected with the notion that people should look after themselves and their close families and not rely on others in society or the government. Kids used to learn an "I" perspective and begin to rely on themselves as much as possible, both financially and socially. As a result, kids typically leave the family at a certain age, and the relationship between father, mother, and children begins to deteriorate. (Hofstede, 2010) (Country comparison, 2017). In the case of Turkey (37), it's mostly a collectivist society. That reveals the word "we" is significant there because people belong to different groups like families, clans, or organizations and look after one another in exchange for allegiance. The bond or relationship has a moral foundation, which mostly takes precedence over the different parts of personal, social, and professional life (Country Comparison, 2017).

Individualism and family ties and psychological issues in the US and Turkey

Based on the IDV score and analytical perspective, this research can assume that the United States, as a highly individualistic country, is expected to have a higher divorce rate and more single parents, whereas Turkey will have a lower divorce rate and fewer single parents, which will determine the family ties of both countries. According to Table 1, the United States has one of the highest divorce rates in the world, with 2.7% per 1000 people, ranking 13th in the world. Turkey, on the other hand, has 1.6% and a position of 60, which is obviously on the lower end of divorce percentages and outside of the studies' Top Fifty measurement. Similarly, Map 1 illustrates that the United States (23 %) has the highest percentage of children living with a single parent, while the global average is 6.8 %, and Turkey (2 %) has one of the world's lowest single-parent children rates. It can be clearly said from these two types of family relationships that the United States, as the most individualist country in the world, has extremely loose family ties, whereas Turkey, as a collectivist country, has very strong family bonds, as expected.

For the last part of the study, following the trends of divorce rate and single-parent children percentages, one can understand that the USA will face more depression and suicide, and Turkey is supposed to have lower percentages in both surveys. According to our data (Table 2), the US is also one of the most depressed countries in the world; 5.9% of the total population is facing depression, which is 4th in the world (179 countries). In terms of suicide, the US has a little bit of exception, though that is not high. It has 24th position in the list, and 16.1% of people are most likely to commit suicide among every 1,00,000 people, which is a high percentage and almost in the top part of our Top Ninety measurement. While the global suicide average is 3.4%, Turkey has only 2.4%, which is one of the lowest in terms of world data, and it is in the 169th position. In the same way, the suicide ratio of Turkey (4.4%) is on the lowest side of the world, while this country ranked 100th in a global view (179 countries). This also demonstrates that Turkey is not among the Top Ninety nations. However, when compared to the other three factors, Turkey ranks better in terms of depression proportion. Our findings show that, in contrast to the United States, Turkish people are more likely to experience less depression and suicide. Americans are more likely to experience more depression and suicide, and without a massive cultural transformation, both countries will be on the opposite side of our chosen factors.

Theoretical Interpretation and Discussion

As this research identified a relationship pattern from quantitative descriptive analysis, this section provides a theoretical interpretation based on the lenses and framework of individualism, collectivism and their impacts on family structure and socio-psychological issues. As three main themes are explored from the study's literature review, the theoretical interpretation is also presented based on those themes, which are individualism vs. family cohesion, freedom and social isolation, and family and social support.

Individualism vs. family cohesion

The pattern of the quantitative data from the study reveals that countries with higher IDV scores tend to have higher divorce rates and high numbers of single-parent households. For instance, the USA is one of the highest individualist countries in the IDV index (91), and it has high rates of divorce (2.7% and 13th) and single-parent (23%) households. That suggests a weakening family structure in individualist societies. That can be explained by the trend of emphasizing *personal autonomy* and *self-actualization*, which are essential features of individualism. More focus on individual goals, personal freedom, and self-expression in individual societies sometimes overlooks the collective role and familial responsibilities (Hofstede & Minkov, 2010). That aligns with the difference between individualism and collectivism, as Trandis (1995) stated. People in more individualist societies are encouraged to achieve personal well-being and desire rather than maintain close relationships with families. That has impacts on marriage stability and family bonding, which can lead to higher divorce rates and single-parent households in individualist countries. Cherlin (2010) suggested that nowadays, modern individualistic societies usually see marriage and family as optional and very flexible, which can be adjusted or managed through the fulfillment of personal accomplishment and happiness. Eckersley R & K. (2002) shows that the effect of individualism leads to more divorce and suicide. Gu et al. (2022) and Beck & Beck-Gernsheim (2002) also support that family well-being and social support for network are disrupted because of societal influence for more independence. This mindset shows a significant shift in the mindset of individuals in more individualist countries like the USA and the UK, leading to many divorces and broken families. In these societies, marriage is often seen just as a social contract, not anything like an essential, lifelong commitment. Therefore, it gets broken easily when colluded with personal satisfaction (Kalmijn, 2007). However, weakening family ties not only resembles the changing nature of society but also suggests that it has a deep route in cultural norms where *the self* is more emphasized than *the family* (Hofstede et al., 2010).

Freedom and Social Isolation

The current study suggests that there is a huge psychological cost of individualism, indicating a relationship between *personal autonomy* and *socio-psychological distress* because countries with higher individualism scores have higher rates of depression and suicide. One of our comparative cases is that as an individualistic nation, the USA also has a high percentage of depression (5.9% and 4th) and suicide ((16.1% and 24th) compared to other nations worldwide. Individualism may have promoted a high level of *freedom of choice, self-dependence*, and *tyranny of choices*, yet it can easily lead to *social isolation, high expectations*, and *lack of support network*, which can contribute to less satisfaction and stress transferred to higher depression (Schwartz, 2000). Hidika (2012) also extends the argument and suggests that modern individualistic societies nowadays feature a rising level of depression and anxiety because of a continuous erosion of *the social support system*, specifically *family cohesion*. Higher anxiety and depression rate always somehow influences more suicidal tendencies of individuals. Several studies have identified the effect that more individualism leads to social disruption through different mental health issues, such as Eckersley R & K. (2002)'s findings about suicide; Nezlek & Humphrey (2023) shows the relationship with neuroticism, anxiety, interpersonal relationships, Scott et al. (2004) finds psychological drawback; Twenge (2011) shows anxiousness and depression and so on.

Family as a Protective Factor

This study suggests that Turkey has a lower rank in the IDV index (37), which indicates the collective nature of Turkish society, and also has a significantly lower percentage of divorce (1.6% and 60th in 107 countries), single-parent households (2%), depression (2.4% and 169th in 179), and suicide (4.4% and 100th in 179). Similarly, most individualist countries have a high percentage of divorce and single-parent rates, depression, and suicide rates. That indicates that collectivist countries have a better position in the survey. As a whole, that resembles the influence of *family and interdependence*, which work as a strong *social support system*, including emotional, financial, and psychological support systems. That acts as a protective measure against mental health issues like depression and the tendency of *social isolation* (Triandis, 1995). The study of Kitayama and Markus (1995) also suggests that in collectivist societies, *the self* is defined by interdependence and contributes to a strong sense of belonging to family and societal responsibilities. A number of studies find (i.e., Debra Thomeer (2020); Knyazev et al. (2017); Sorys, 2020); Maimon D et al., 2010) that family and

social safety nets provide huge psychological benefits for an individual to reduce the amount of stress and anxiety, which eventually has an impact on the level of depression and suicide in those societies. However, some studies find the opposite, that is, mostly while controlling income and economic quality of life.

Practical Implications and limitations of the study

This study emphasizes culturally informed policies and steps by the relevant authority depending on the context. So that they can address the effect of individualism on family where structure and mental health. In highly individualist societies, family bonding is weak because of high divorce and single parents, also socio-psychological issues such as depression and suicide rates are pretty high, policymakers should prioritize policy that helps to work on family bonding and provide an enhanced mental health support system. These include social awareness, proper education, a community support network, family counseling, and so on. Also, there is a need for awareness of cultural adaptation and cultural roots in this era of ever-changing globalization. Collectivist societies also need to be careful and take relevant measures to prevent the multiple other factors embedded in the society, such as economy, social well-being, and avoidance of collective pressure.

To examine limitations, the major one is that this study did not provide any causal relationship between variables of the study (i.e., individualism, divorce, single parents, depression, and suicide rate) Instead of providing descriptive quantitative analysis, using software-based Pearson Correlation analysis or multivariate Regression analysis (OLS) could provide direct relationship through hypothesis testing. Therefore, study results can not be generalized. Future studies with longitudinal data and inferential analysis could provide robust and more nuanced results. All of the study's data are secondary, which indicates that these data sets may not have captured the full complexity of family dynamics over a variety of cultural contexts. Moreover, there are plenty of other factors and variables that may also influence family ties and socio-psychological issues (i.e., depression and suicide), such as cultural context, economy, religion, education, historical pattern, masculinity and femininity, and so on, as identified by Hofstede (2010), that should be investigated further in subsequent studies. Qualitative studies with small N can bring a deep and context-based analysis in different case-oriented research.

Conclusion

To conclude this research, it can be demonstrated that this study successfully addressed research objectives, and overall, this study observed a relationship pattern between individualism, loosening family ties, and socio-psychological problems in both parts of the study and also compared between the USA and Turkey. This study also described the pattern of relationships based on in-depth theoretical and empirical studies. The findings suggest that highly individualistic countries usually face a high proportion of divorce and single parents. Because of social isolation and ultimate autonomy, they also face a high degree of depression and suicide. Conversely, collective countries like Turkey have a lower rate of divorce and single-parent households. They also have a lower percentage of depression and suicide. This suggests decisive policy steps to prevent the issues related to this study. Further psychological, cultural, and policy studies can shed light on the problems of the policy process regarding family bonding and mental health outcomes in different or global contexts.

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